

EXHIBIT OF SPIRITUAL DESTRUCTION IN SOCIETY**Г.Бекмуродова***(Karshi State University)*

Abstract: The article discusses the content and main manifestations of spiritual destruction. According to the author, spiritual destruction manifests itself in a variety of factors that disrupt the process of spiritual production, destroy forms of social consciousness and negatively affect social psychology and ideology.

Key words: destruction, social destruction, spiritual destruction, factors that disrupt the process of spiritual production, factors that destroy forms of social consciousness, factors that negatively affect social psychology and ideology.

Today, a series of negative trends are observed in the world ideological processes, and the ideological struggle between different political forces is reaching its peak. Consequently, the more constructive processes increase in the spiritual sphere of human society, the more destructive elements are manifested. In this regard, there is a need to study in detail the laws of destructive situations in the spiritual sphere.

In socially destructive processes, the law of unity and struggle of opposites is manifested; in particular, progress and regression, progress and decline, positivity and negativity, creativity and destruction are mutually demanding aspects of social reality; as the scope of progress, development, positivity, and creativity expands and accelerates, regression, decline, negativity, and destruction take root;

In socially destructive processes, the law of negation of negation is manifested; during the first norm, destruction acquires certain properties and content, during the second norm they are destroyed; in the third norm "Some (most important) properties and contents existing during Norm 1 and Norm 2 are combined (synthesized)".

Socially destructive processes and situations can be manifested in various areas of society. In all areas, it occurs as a factor that erodes the main features of the system and undermines its stability. The spiritual sphere of society is no exception.

When thinking about the spiritual sphere of society, the forms of social consciousness are usually mentioned first. In fact, this field is somewhat complicated. In our opinion, it is better to start the interpretation of the specific features of the spiritual sphere of society from the process of spiritual production. Because spiritual production is a type of collective activity aimed at creating different imaginations, moods, knowledge, ideas, theories, teachings, and values. Like material production, it has its own functions. In particular, spiritual production fulfills the tasks of improving various spheres of society's life, producing socially important knowledge and ideas, raising the level of knowledge of society members about these knowledge and ideas, shaping public opinion, and resolving people's spiritual needs.

The process of spiritual production ends with the emergence of various imaginations, knowledge, ideas, theories, doctrines, values, and the decision of the attitude towards them. These ideas and knowledge, teachings and values are concentrated in forms of social consciousness - political, legal, ethical, aesthetic, religious, scientific, philosophical and other consciousness. Any form of social consciousness is a product of understanding reality in its own way and embodies the ideas and views common to people of a certain period.

The manifestation of imaginations, knowledge, ideas and values accumulated in forms of social consciousness is called social psychology, and its manifestation at the theoretical level is called ideology. Social psychology consists of a collection of feelings, experiences, moods, knowledge, habits, and traditions that are formed during the daily life of society members and do not have a specific system. In contrast, ideology is a generalized, systematized, theorized set of knowledge and ideas.

Thus, the spiritual sphere of society includes three features: a) it includes the process of spiritual production; b) it is composed of different forms of social consciousness; c) it consists of a unique synthesis of social psychology and ideology. Any factor that threatens the stability of these characteristics is destruction. Destruction in the spiritual realm will consist of:

a) disconnection of the spiritual production process from the needs of society; the spiritual production process itself, which ends with the formation of knowledge and ideas that do not serve the development of society, is spiritual destruction;

b) weakening of the process of production of socially important knowledge and ideas; entanglement of the process of spiritual production with the creation of knowledge that does not have any significance is the starting point of the spiritual crisis of society;

c) decrease in the level of awareness of new knowledge and ideas of society members; the decrease in people's awareness of the newly emerging knowledge and ideas leads to the rooting of ignorance, dilettantism, populism, corruption and many other social ills in society;

g) formation of wrong public opinion; public opinion, which is a specific form of public consciousness, is a specific indicator of people's attitude to social reality; its violation in a purposeful manner does not allow for a correct assessment of social processes;

d) negative changes in people's spiritual needs; the roots of needs that do not serve the moral growth of citizens are one of the biggest factors that threaten the moral security of society;

e) negative trends in social psychology; such trends may be associated with the emergence of a depressed mood in society, the emergence of harmful habits, the establishment of irrational traditions, and so on;

j) negative trends in social ideology; such tendencies can be manifested as a loss of people's trust in ideologies in society, ideological indifference, and an increase in the influence of destructive ideas.

So, spiritual destruction is manifested in various factors aimed at eroding the specific characteristics of the spiritual existence of the society and disrupting its stability. Its main manifestations are related to the factors that disrupt the process of spiritual production, hinder the development of forms of social consciousness, and have a negative impact on social psychology and ideology. In order to ensure the stable social development of the society, it is necessary to think carefully about the ways to eliminate these destructive situations.

References

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